

Geology in Motion: The Effects of Warfare on Geology

PART 1

BOMBTURBATION

DALLIN LAYCOCK, SEAN FLETCHER, PAUL BREMNER, ERIN PEMBERTON, AIDEN WOO, RICHARD MACKENZIE

INTRODUCTION

Warfare has not only shaped human history but also transformed the very ground beneath our feet. While battles are often depicted as clashes of armies and strategies, an often-overlooked factor in military operations is the influence of geology. From ancient times to modern conflicts, the terrain has played a crucial role, altering the course of history in profound and lasting ways. In any battlefield, understanding the land in terms of features, canalizing lanes, avenues of approach and obtaining the high ground provides a distinct advantage. In addition to the surficial features, military geologists have been tasked with characterizing the subsurface by drilling water wells, finding suitable building materials, evaluating substrates for military vehicles, and excavating tunnels. Many of these military applications have played a significant role in shaping the outcomes of wars throughout history. However, a related, and equally overlooked topic is the lasting effects of warfare on the terrain itself. This article, the first installment of this series, focuses on exploring unique examples of landscapes changed through warfare, specifically the impact that bombs have had on earth's surface.

EXAMPLE 1

Pointe Du Hoc: Operation Overlord was the monumental invasion of German-occupied France, designed to turn the tides of WWII against the Nazis. Allied troops from the United States, Canada, the United Kingdom, and other countries stormed the beaches of Normandy on June 6, 1944 in what was the largest seaborne invasion in history. Army Rangers were tasked with taking a vantage point between Utah Beach and Omaha Beach on the top of a Cretaceous limestone cliff called Pointe du Hoc.

This prominent cliff-top position was heavily fortified by the German forces, and bristling with artillery and machine guns. Its elevated location provided a commanding view of the

surrounding coastline, making it a potential threat to landing beaches. American Army Rangers undertook a daring assault to scale the limestone cliffs with rope ladders and capture Pointe du Hoc. However, the main alteration to the landscape was caused by pre-invasion bombing by the 9th Air Force A-20 Havoc bombers. The heavy bombing left the area pockmarked with metre-scale craters, creating a terrain occasionally referred to as "Bombturbation" (Figure 1).

EXAMPLE 2

Tunneling in WWI and the Lochnagar Crater: Excavating and tunneling in WWI was a common practice (Doyle, 2014, Deiderichs and Hutchinson, 2021). Trench warfare is perhaps

the most well-known example of excavation in WWI, but tunnels through underlying bedrock were also commonly used to transport troops, supplies, and even to deliver explosives behind enemy lines. As discussed by Laycock et al. (2023), tunneling at Vimy Ridge provides an excellent example of the use of this tactic in WWI. The tunnels from that battle are still there, along with inscriptions from soldiers on the walls. The permanence of those excavations is debatable, as occasional collapses occur, and create hazards for visitors to the memorial at Vimy Ridge (Hutchinson et al. 2008).

The prelude to the deadly Battle of the Somme included extensive tunneling by both sides of the battle. The bedrock of the Somme is comprised primarily of relatively soft

chalk, which facilitated excavations (Figure 2). Tunneling under “no man’s land” was dangerous, as explosions from surface battles, or from adjacent enemy tunnels, could cave in the underground mining operations on the miners. Another risk was directly encountering the enemy’s tunnel, which could result in brutal hand to hand combat underground.

In 1916, the 185th Tunneling Company started work on the “Lochnagar” mine in November of 1915. The tunnel started approximately 91 m behind the British front line, which was only 270 m away from the German front line, reaching a total depth of around 29 m. Maintaining silence was a top priority for the miners, who feared being detected by enemy miners. They worked barefoot, using primarily bayonets to scrape away at the chalk, averaging only around 46 cm of progress per day (Edmonds, 1993). Eventually the mine was finished and was packed with 27 tons of explosives. On July 1, 1916, the first day of the Battle of the Somme, the explosives were detonated, creating a crater that was 140 m across and 30m deep (Sheldon, 2006).

Tunneling in WWI also has had a lasting geological impact in other ways. Early geophysical techniques were used to triangulate enemy artillery positions. They would also hold a geophone to their ears to listen for enemy tunneling operations (Gendzwill, 2007). Many craters from WWI were eventually filled in to reclaim the land, but the Lochnagar crater has been preserved to honor those who fought.

EXAMPLE 3

Project Plowshare: Perhaps the most extreme example of “bomburbation” is found in Nevada. Project Plowshare was a product of the Cold War, initiated in the 1950s by the United States Atomic Energy Commission, aimed to explore peaceful applications of nuclear weapons. Specifically, it focused on using nuclear devices for large-scale engineering projects, such as mining, excavation, and creating artificial harbors. The idea was to harness the immense energy released by nuclear explosions to reshape the Earth’s surface (refer to US department of energy report DOE/NV--209-REV 15). However, due to environmental and safety concerns, most of these plans were eventually abandoned, leaving behind a series of craters in the Nevada desert (Figure 4).

“Storax Sedan” was one such nuclear test, performed on July 6, 1962 using a

FIGURE 1: A) Cliffs at Pointe Du Hoc. Army Rangers were tasked with the dangerous mission of scaling these Jurassic-aged cliffs under enemy attack. B) Craters near the fortifications at Pointe Du Hoc show an example of “Bomburbation”.

FIGURE 2: Illustrated cross section of the generalized geology of the Somme region. Blue arrows show fighting trenches with favorable locations in terms of drainage, red arrows show trenches with poor drainage locations. Orange arrows show deep dugouts with poor drainage, and purple arrows show deep dugouts with favorable drainage. The green arrows indicate the fighting tunnels in the chalk, which are those which would have been mined for detonation of explosives and delivering troops behind enemy lines.

FIGURE 3: Google Earth image of the Lochnagar Crater. North is up, and scale is as shown.

thermonuclear device, which was lowered into a 194 m deep borehole, drilled into the alluvium. The blast had a yield of 435 terajoules and displaced more than 11,000,000 tons of soil. The blast was powerful enough to create the largest man-made crater in the United States, measuring 390m in diameter with a depth of 98m. The surrounding area is also pockmarked with smaller craters from the

other 35 warheads detonated during Project Plowshare.

In the Soviet Union, atomic tests were conducted at the Semipalatinsk Test Site in northeast Kazakhstan. 456 nuclear tests were conducted, with severe impacts to the local population and environment. Satellite imagery reveals a terrain covered in craters, similar to that created by Project Plowshare in Nevada.

EXAMPLE 4

Trinitite: Trinitite is a unique glass-like substance first documented in the desert sand at the Trinity test site in New Mexico, where the world's first nuclear bomb detonation occurred on July 16, 1945. The intense heat of the explosion, estimated to be around 1,470 °C (2,680 °F), melted the arkosic sand, resulting in the creation of a layer of green glass that is mildly radioactive (Eby et al. 2010). Initially green in color due to its composition, variations of trinitite include red, attributed to copper from the bomb's electrical wiring, and rare black specimens. Trinitite itself has no crystal structure, and therefore does not qualify as a mineral.

The formation process involved sand being drawn up into the fireball, melting, and then raining down in a liquid form before resolidifying (Hermes and Strickfaden, 2005). The study of trinitite provides valuable insights into the effects of nuclear detonations on geology. Within the glass, unmelted quartz grains are encapsulated alongside radionuclides formed during the blast, offering a snapshot of the momentous explosion.

CONCLUSIONS

The interplay between geology and warfare is a multifaceted and often underappreciated aspect of military history. As explored in this article, the impact of bombs and other military activities have left indelible marks on the landscape, with physical and historical imprints

Figure 4: A) Google Earth image of craters from Project Plowshare in Nevada. The red arrow shows the Storax Sedan crater. Other smaller craters are visible toward the bottom of the image. B) Google Earth image of craters from similar nuclear bomb experiments in northeast Kazakhstan.

FIGURE 5: Image of trinitite samples. The original image did not include a scale, but the fragments range in size from approximately 1 to 3 cm in diameter. Image courtesy of Shaddack - CC BY 3.0, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=5935485>

that endure long after the conflicts have ended. At Pointe du Hoc, the fierce D-day battle scarred the cliffs, leaving craters and remnants of the fortifications that bear witness to the conflict. The massive explosion at Lochnager mine during WW1, resulting from extensive strategic tunneling, permanently transformed the landscape, creating a vast crater that stands as a testament to the subterranean warfare in the area. Project Plowshare's experimental

nuclear explosions, intended to test application for peaceful engineering and construction had significant geological impacts, illustrating both the potential and peril of using such powerful forces and the alteration that can occur to the Earth. Trinitite, formed by the intense heat of the first nuclear test at New Mexico's Trinity site, symbolizes the profound and sometimes unintended consequences of human actions on the Earth's surface. The huge force and

energy exerted in the discussed examples have reshaped associated landscapes and altered natural processes in ways that underscore the intricate linkages between anthropogenic activity and geological processes. Future installments in this series will delve deeper into the effects of warfare on geology related to flooding and sedimentology.

REFERENCES AND SUGGESTED READINGS:

Deiderichs, M., Hutchinson, D.J. (2020). Tunnel Warfare in World War I: The Underground Battlefield Tunnels of Vimy Ridge, France. Published in *Tunnels and Underground Cities: Engineering and Innovation Meet Archeology, Architecture and Art*, Volume 1. p. 52-61.

Doyle, P. (2014). Geology and the war on the Western Front, 1914–1918. *Geology Today*. Vol. 30, No. 5. Pages 183-191.

Eby, N., Hermes, R., Charnley, N., Smoliga, J.A. (2010). Trinitite – The Atomic Rock. *Geology Today*, Vol. 26, No. 5. P. 180-185.

Edmonds, J. E. (1993). *Military Operations France and Belgium, 1916: Sir Douglas Haig's Command to the 1st July: Battle of the Somme*. History of the Great War Based

on Official Documents by Direction of the Historical Section of the Committee of Imperial Defence. Vol. I. P. 36, 371.

Gendzwill, D. (2007). Vimy Ridge and Geophysics. *CSEG Recorder*, June 2007, Vol. 32 No. 6.

Hermes, R., Strickfaden, W. (2005). New theory on the formation of trinitite. *Nuclear Weapons Journal*, No. 2, p. 2-7.

Hutchinson, D.J., Diederichs, M., Pehme, P., Sawyer, P., Robinson, P., Puxley, A., Robichaud, H. (2008). Geomechanics stability assessment of World War I military excavations at the Canadian National Vimy Memorial Site, France. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*. Vol 45, No. 1, P. 59-77.

Laycock, D.P., Fletcher, S., Pemberton, E., Bremner, P., Mackenzie, R. (2023). *Geology in Motion: The Geology of the Battle of Vimy Ridge*. CEGA Reservoir 2003 No. 6. P. 26-31.

Rosenbaum, M.S. (1989). Geological Influence on Tunnelling Under the Western Front at Vimy Ridge. *Proceedings of the Geologists' Association*. 100 (1). P. 135 – 140.

Sheldon, J. (2006). *The German Army on the Somme 1914–1916* (Pen & Sword Military ed.). London: Leo Cooper. ISBN 978-1-84415-269-8.

United States Nuclear Tests; July 1945 through September 1992, DOE/NV--209-REV 15 December 2000